

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:156267AC-6343-4502-9E1B-5600A298EDB9>
DOI: 10.24412/2226-0773-2021-10-8-1117-1120

**Interesting species of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera:
Cerambycidae) from China in the collection of S. Murzin. Part 2**

M.A. Lazarev¹, S.V. Murzin², M.-Y. Lin³

¹Free Economic Society of Russia, Department of Scientifics Conferences and All-Russian Projects

Tverskaya str., 22a, Moscow 125009 Russia

e-mail: cerambycidae@bk.ru, humanityspace@gmail.com

²Proletarsky prosp. 8, build. 1, apart. 23, Moscow 115522 Russia

e-mail: murka3@list.ru

³Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Key Laboratory of Zoological Systematics and Evolution

1-5 Beichen West Road, Chaoyang Dist., Beijing 100101 China

e-mail: linmeiying@ioz.ac.cn

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, zoogeography, new records, China.

Abstract: 6 Cerambycidae species are newly recorded for different provinces of China.

Introduction

We continue identification and study of enormous Cerambycidae collection preserved in the apartment of S. Murzin (Moscow). The identifications of the species were arranged by the authors. The distributional data for each taxon are based on the publication by Lin and Yang (2019).

List of identified species

Demonax viduatus Holzschuh, 2009

Fig. 1

Material. 1 female, China, Guangxi Province, Gongcheng, Mt. Dayaoshan, 1-15.06.2002.

Distribution. China: Yunnan (Wenshan county, Laojun Mts), Guangxi (new record), NE Laos (Hua Phan Province).

M.A. Lazarev, S.V. Murzin, M.-Y. Lin

Leiopus (Carinopus) holzschuhi Wallin, Kvamme & Lin, 2012

Fig. 2

Material. 1 female, China, Shaanxi Province, Houzhenzi, 1350-2000 m, 27.5.-8.6.1999. S. Murzin leg.

Distribution. China: Henan, Shaanxi, Chongqing, Sichuan, Guizhou (Wallin, Kvamme, Lin, 2012).

Leiopus (Carinopus) fallaciosus Holzschuh, 1993

Fig. 3

Material. 2 males 7 females, Guangdong, Nanling, 8.5.2009 - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IZCAS); 1 male 2 females, Fujian, Meihuashan, 6.07 - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IZCAS).

Distribution. China: Jiangxi, Fujian, Guangdong (Wallin, Kvamme, Lin, 2012).

Remarks. Wallin, Kvamme & Lin (2012) reported Guangdong based on 1 male and 2 females from Nanling on page 3, however, they did not include Guangdong on page 18. Then, Lin and Yang (2019) only included the type locality Fujian while missed both Jiangxi and Guangdong. Here we confirmed this species is distributed in Fujian, Jiangxi and Guangdong.

Paraniphona rotundipennis Breuning 1974

Fig. 4

Material. 1 female, China, Shaanxi Province, Houzhenzi, 1350-2000 m, 27.5.-8.6.1999, S.Murzin leg.

Distribution. China: Shaanxi (new record), Gansu.

Xylariopsis mimica Bates 1884

Fig. 5

Material. 1 female, China, Sichuan Province, Nanping environs, 33.2589°N, 104.2236°E, 1800 m, 17-21.7.2013, M.Murzin & O.Shulga leg.; 1 male, Gansu, Zhengning, Zhongwan, 20-30.7.1979, Xiao-Hua Wang leg. - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese

M.A. Lazarev, S.V. Murzin, M.-Y. Lin

Academy of Sciences (IZCAS); 2 males 2 females, Beijing, Yanqing, Songshan, 10.6.2011 - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IZCAS); 1 male, Beijing, Yanqing, Badaling Senlingongyuan, 20.8.2015, Yong Wang leg. - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IZCAS).

Distribution. China: Beijing, Gansu, Jiangsu, Sichuan (new record), Shaanxi, Shanghai; Russia: Far East; Japan; ?North Korea; South Korea.

Xylotrechus (s str.) *incurvatus incurvatus* (Chevrolat, 1863)

Fig. 6

Material. 1 female, China, Guangxi, Gongcheng, Mt. Dayaoshan, 1-15.6.2002; 1 female, Guangxi, Jinxiu, Huawangshanzhuang, 600 m, 20.5.1999, Hui Xiao leg. - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IZCAS); 1 female, Guangxi, Jinxiu, Luoxiang, 200 m, 15.5.1999, Yanzhou Zhang leg. - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IZCAS); 1 male, Guangxi, Jinxiu, Laoshan, 13.9.1981, Qijing You leg. - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IZCAS); 1 female, Guangxi, Lijunheling, 18.9.1981, Qijing You leg. (IZCAS); 1 female, Guangxi, Longsheng, Baiyan, 1150 m, 18.6.1963, Shuyong Wang leg. - collection of Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (IZCAS).

Distribution. China: Fujian Gansu, Guandong, Guangxi (new record), Hebei, Hongkong, Hunan, Xizang (Tibet), Yunnan, Sichuan, Taiwan; South Korea (Mt. Soyosan); India: Sikkim, Darjeeling District; ?Bhutan; ?Nepal; Myanmar.

REFERENCES

- Danilevsky M.L. 2020 (ed.). Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, vol. 6 (1), Chrysomeloidea I (Vesperidae, Disteniidae, Cerambycidae). Revised and updated edition. Leiden / Boston: Brill, i-xxii, 1-712.
- Lin M.-Y. [Meiying] and Yang X.-K. [Xingke] 2019. Catalogue of Chinese Coleoptera volume 9. Chrysomeloidea: Vesperidae, Disteniidae, Cerambycidae. Beijing: Science Press: i-xii, 575 pp.
- Wallin H., Kvamme T., Lin M.-Y. [Meiying] 2012. A review of the genera *Leiopus* Audinet-Serville, 1835 and *Acanthocinus* Dejean, 1821 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, Acanthocinini) in Asia, with descriptions of six new species of *Leiopus* from China. - Zootaxa. Auckland 3326: 1-36.

Fig. 1 *Demonax viduatus* Holzschuh, 2009 from Guangxi.

Fig. 2 *Leiopus (Carinopus) holzschuhi* Wallin, Kvamme & Lin, 2012 from Shaanxi.

Fig. 3 *Leiopus (Carinopus) fallaciosus* Holzschuh, 1993 from Guangdong.

Fig. 4 *Paraniphona rotundipennis* Breuning, 1974 from Shaanxi.

Fig. 5 *Xylariopsis mimica* Bates, 1884 from Sichuan.

Fig. 6 *Xylotrechus* (s str.) *incurvatus incurvatus* (Chevrolat, 1863) from Guangxi.

Received: 10.05.2021

Accepted: 18.08.2021